

Polarographic Studies on the Complexes of Zn, Cd and Pb with Thiovanol

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The complex formation of Zn(II), Cd(II) and Pb(II) with thiovanol has been studied polarographically in acetate buffer which shows a stoichiometry of 1:2: Metal:Ligand. Zn(II) gives an irreversible, Cd(II) a quasireversible and Pb(II) a reversible reduction wave in acetate buffer. The forward rate constant k_f^0 in case of Zn and Cd have been found to be 7.768×10^{-10} moles litre⁻¹ sec⁻¹ and 3.477×10^{-10} moles litre⁻¹ sec⁻¹ respectively. The dissociation constant for the Pb-TV complex ion being 3.9×10^{-3} . The transfer coefficient (α) for Cd-TV complex is 0.681.

THE present interest on compounds containing sulphhydryl group is due to their usefulness in medicine¹, biology², industry³, and analytical chemistry¹⁰. In continuation of our work on complexes of thiovanol with transition metals^{11, 12} the present paper describes the polarographic studies on the complexes of thiovanol (CH₂SHCHOHCH₂OH) with Zn, Cd and Pb in aqueous medium. The results of studies show that metal : ligand ratios in the complexes are 1 : 2. The forward rate constants, for Zn-TV and Cd-TV complexes, transfer coefficient for Cd-TV complex and the dissociation constant for Pb-TV complex have been calculated. (TV=Thiovanol).

Materials and Methods

Stock solutions of lead nitrate and cadmium sulphate were prepared in double distilled water from BDH analaR grade and that of Zinc was prepared by dissolving Zinc Oxide BDH analaR in minimum quantity of dilute HCl. All experiments were done in aqueous medium. All the measurements were made at $26^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$ in air-free media and under nitrogen atmosphere.

Polarographic measurements were made using a manual circuit as recommended by Kolthoff and Lingane⁴. Measurements were made with Hume and Harris⁵ saturated Calomel electrode as reference electrode. The characteristics of the d.m.e. capillary used were as follows :

$$m = 2.012 \text{ mg/sec} \quad t = 3.70 \text{ seconds}$$

$$m^{\frac{2}{3}} t^{\frac{1}{6}} = 2.003 \text{ mg}^{\frac{2}{3}} \text{sec}^{-\frac{1}{6}}$$

height of the mercury column $h = 36.4$ cm. Studies were made in acetate buffer. A Leeds Northrup pH meter, with a general purpose glass electrode was used for the pH measurements. All the other Chemicals used were of analaR grade.

Results and Discussions

Polarographic measurements on the complexes were made in aqueous medium and acetate buffer (pH 4.8) and at a constant ionic strength $\mu = 0.2M$ in the presence of KNO₃ as supporting electrolyte.

Fig. 1. System Zinc-TV

Half-wave potential ($E_{1/2}$) values for Zn-TV (-1.05 volt Vs SCE), Pb-TV(-0.425 volt Vs SCE) and Cd-TV (-0.63 volt Vs SCE) were observed to shift towards more negative potentials. The values obtained for the $E_{1/2}$ of the complexed metal ions in different concentrations of the ligand are given in Table 1.

TABLE-1 CHARACTERISTICS OF THE WAVES OF ZINC, CADMIUM AND LEAD IONS IN THE PRESENCE OF TV (METAL ION CONCENTRATION $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$)

Zinc-TV		Cadmium-TV		Lead-TV	
[TV] $M \times 10^{-3}$	$E_{1/2}$ (V)	[TV] $M \times 10^{-3}$	$E_{1/2}$ (V)	[TV] $M \times 10^{-3}$	$E_{1/2}$ (V)
2.16	-1.0625	2.16	-0.6425	2.16	-0.4315
4.32	-1.0715	4.32	-0.6450	4.32	-0.4400
6.48	-1.0750	6.48	-0.6500	6.48	-0.4450
8.64	-1.0770	8.64	-0.6580	8.64	-0.4475
10.80	-1.0770	10.80	-0.6580	10.80	-0.4475

Zn-TV complex: Zn (II) gave a two electron irreversible reduction wave. The plot of $\log i/i_d - i$ Vs $E_{1/2}$ gave a straight line with slope 0.060 volt (Fig 1). This proves the irreversibility of the system. The plot of $E_{1/2}$ Vs $\log C$ of thiovanol was a straight line with a slope of 0.071 volt (Fig 2). The following electrode reaction may be proposed.

Fig.2- System Zinc-TV

contribution of TV has been ignored.

The kinetic parameters of the irreversible and quasireversible wave can be studied by Matsuda and Ayabe equation¹⁷.

$$(E_{1/2})C = \frac{0.06}{\alpha n} \left[\log \frac{K_f}{\sqrt{D_N}} f_N + \frac{1}{2} \log T - 0.053 - \log \left(\frac{i_l}{i_d} \right) - (N-P) \log f_x C_x \right] \dots (1)$$

where $(E_{1/2})C$ = Half-wave potential Vs NHE, K_f = forward rate constant at potential of NHE, D_N = diffusion coefficient of complex ion in solution, T = droptime at $E_{1/2}$, i_d = diffusion current, i_l = limiting current, f_N = activity coefficient of complex ion, f_x = activity coefficient of ligand, C_x = concentration of ligand

and f_N and $f_x = 1 \left(\frac{i_l}{i_d} \right) = 1$. The value of K_f for ZnTV system has been found to be 7.768×10^{10} litre⁻¹ sec⁻¹.

Pb-TV complex: Pb(II) gave a two electron, reversible reduction wave. A plot of $\log (i/i_d - i)$ Vs $E_{1/2}$ gave a straight line with a slope of 0.030V (Fig 3). The plot of $E_{1/2}$ Vs $\log C$ of TV gave a slope of 0.056 V (Fig 4).

FIG.3 System Lead-TV

Applying the equation⁸

$$\frac{dE_{1/2}}{d \log [TV]} = \frac{0.060}{n} (p-q) \dots (2)$$

where n is the number of electrons involved in the reduction, p and q are number of ligand groups attached to the oxidised and reduced forms respectively. The value of p was found to be very nearly two when $q=0$ and $n=2$ in equation (2). The value of

dissociation constant was calculated using Lingane⁹ equation and came out to be 3.9×10^{-5} . The electrode reaction may be represented as $Pb(TV)_2^{2+} + 2e^- \rightleftharpoons Pb(Hg) + 2TV$ (Charge contribution of TV +Hg has been ignored).

FIG.4. System Lead-TV

Cd-TV complex: Cd(II) gave a two electron quasi-reversible reduction wave. The plot of $\log(i/i_d - i)$ gave a straight line with a slope of 0.044 V which is higher than the value expected for two electron reversible reduction (0.0296 V at 30° (Fig.5)). The plot of $E_{1/2}$ Vs $\log C$ of TV was a straight line with a slope of 0.045 V (Fig 6). Thus the electrode is not reversible and may be treated as quasireversible. The value of transfer coefficient (α) came out to be 0.681. The forward rate constant (K^0_f) was found to be 3.477×10^{-18} moles liter⁻¹ sec⁻¹ using Matsuda and Ayabe equation¹⁷. The electrode reaction may thus be proposed as

(Where charge contribution of TV has been ignored).

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Fig.5. System cadmium TV

Fig.6. System cadmium TV

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